

Comparative Assessment of the Effects of Selected Organophosphate Pesticides on Cauliflower and Cabbage Crops Grown in Ajmer, Rajasthan

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The present investigation was made to assess the effect of top 3 widely used organophosphate pesticides on cauliflower and cabbage crops grown in Ajmer. The selection of the vegetables was based on the area of cultivation and the scale of production. The range of residues of different organophosphate pesticides was found in the order of malathion > dimethoate > monocrotophos. Comparative assessment of the low dose (2 ppm) and high dose (5 ppm) of each selected pesticides was studied on both vegetables grown in the greenhouse and compared with the controlled crop of each vegetable, which was not treated with any dose of these pesticides. Results of the investigation revealed that the average concentrations of different phyto-chemical parameters including starch, lipids, protein, carotenoids, chlorophyll-a, chlorophyll-b, etc., in selected vegetables were decreased on increasing the level of concentration of various pesticides.

KEYWORD

Cabbage, Cauliflower, Dimethoate, Malathion, Monocrotophos, Organophosphate pesticides.

INTRODUCTION

The application of high intensity of synthetic pesticides has become a serious cause of concern in recent years. For the past 5 decades humans have almost been dependent upon synthetic or organic pesticides. After 'green revolution', the pesticide consumption in India has increased rapidly. The global share of India, in vegetable production is about 13.4%. Surveys indicated that 50-70% of total vegetables produced in India are contaminated with pesticide residues (Karanth, 2002). Total 14% of the pesticides consumed in the country are used for vegetable production. It is reported that, in Indian agriculture system, organophosphate pesticides (50%) are mostly consumed, followed by pyrethroids (19%), organochlorines (18%), carbamates (4%) and biopesticides (1%) (Dhaliwal and Singh,

2000). Cabbage (*Brassica oleraceae* var. *capitata*) and cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea* var. *botrytis*) are 2 major vegetables produced and consumed in India (Weinberge and Srinivasan, 2009). Both, cabbage and cauliflower are grown in 232,800 ha and 278,800 ha area, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2007). The excessive use of pesticides has geared-up due to high pest infestation in these vegetables. In India, it has been reported that Diamondback moth (DBM), *Plutella xylostella*, is the common pest in almost all production areas of cabbage and cauliflower with reported losses of upto 50% of total production (Grzywacz *et al.*, 2010; Sandur, 2004). Organophosphates pesticides are prime choice to combat with such pests in region. Earlier studies carried out in Ajmer region shows that percentage of area concerned with cauliflower and cabbage cultivation shares about 30% of total vegetable crops (Charan *et al.*, 2010; Tiwari, 1995). Therefore, one of the objectives of the study was to find out the residue levels of commonly applied organophosphate pesticides in these crops.

Figure 1. Location of sampling sites in Ajmer

Vegetable crop have their specific nutritional profile of edible parts. A nutritive value with respect to calories, carbohydrates, proteins, fats, vitamins, and minerals in edible part was published by National Institute of Nutrition, ICMR, Hyderabad. Excessive use of synthetic pesticides may degrade the nutritional profile of the edible commodities including vegetables. Indiscriminate use of such pesticides in Indian agriculture system varies from region to region, depending on poor educational status of public, lack of general awareness about pesticide toxicity, less alertness about physico-chemical properties of soil, lack of effective training programmes on good agricultural practices (GAPs) for farmers as well as pesticide dealers and quality of water used for irrigation, etc., (Bhanti and Taneja, 2005). The present research was focused on the assessment of effect of different organophosphate pesticides on nutritive value of cabbage and cauliflower crops grown in Ajmer. The effort was also made to assess the residual level of selected organophosphate pesticides in both the vegetables in natural environment.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Design of the present investigation

A survey was conducted to assess the

commonly used organophosphate pesticide in the Ajmer region. The survey was focused on personal interviews with both the farmers and pesticide dealers of the Ajmer city. Based on the results of the survey, top 3 organophosphate pesticides were selected for assessing their effect on phyto-chemical parameters of cabbage and cauliflower, which may alter the nutritional values of these vegetables. The selection of the vegetables was based on the scale of production and area of cultivation of the vegetables in the region. Comparative assessment of the low dose (2 ppm) and high dose (5 ppm) of each selected pesticides was studied on both the commodities grown in the greenhouse and compared with the controlled crop, which was not treated with any dose of these pesticides. The residue level of targeted pesticides in natural environment was also studied. For this purpose, total 80 samples of both, cabbage (*Brassica oleraceae* var. *capitata*) and cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea* var. *botrytis*) were collected randomly from different sampling sites of Ajmer (Figure 1). These samples were collected during October 2010 to March 2011. The contamination level of targeted organophosphate pesticides in each commodity was detected by gas liquid chromatography. The present study was confined to the major vegetable productive

Table 1. Sampling sites and their important Characteristics

Name of site	Important characteristic
Palbichhla	Lowland area in Ajmer city, extensively being used for vegetable production. Wastewater of urban effluent is major source of irrigation. Varieties of vegetables are grown here throughout the year
Ramganj	It is one of the major vegetable production area of the city having good connectivity to urban areas. Farmers of this area are growing vegetables at large scale throughout the year. Wastewater of industrial area and urban effluent is major source of irrigation. Literacy rate among farmers is also very poor. Hence, awareness about pesticide toxicity problem is very low
Kotda	It is one of the backward areas nearby the urban region of Ajmer city. Due to high illiteracy among farmers and high amount of consumption of pesticides, this site was selected for the present investigation
Khanpura	It is the largest area of urban region being used for vegetable production. There was a large pond, which is now converted in agriculture area for vegetable production throughout the year. Hence, it is one of the most prone area for pesticide consumption

area of Ajmer city (Table 1).

Analyses of phyto-chemical parameter

To assess the effect of different doses of the targeted pesticides on cabbage and cauliflower, the quantitative estimation of total chlorophylls (Chl-a and Chl-b) and total carotenoids were done according to standard methods (Arnon, 1949; Plummer, 1978). The starch content was estimated as per the method of Yem and Willis (1954). The effect of pesticides on protein content in vegetables were analyzed by the method developed by Lowry *et al.* (1951), while the total lipids were measured by gravimetric method (Folsch *et al.*, 1957).

Gas liquid chromatography analysis

The residues of different organophosphate pesticides were analyzed using a Chemito gas chromatograph (model 8610) equipped with FID and NP detector, equipped with BPX-608 capillary column (25 m x 0.32 ID x 0.46 Fm). The operating conditions were as per method described by FAO (2002) with some modifications.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The present study was conducted in Ajmer

city of Rajasthan October 2010 to March 2011. About 53 farmers and pesticide dealers were interviewed to obtain information on different types of pesticides used on cabbage and cauliflower crops. It was observed that organophosphate category of pesticides was the first choice of farmers and vegetable growers in the area. There is a large number of different varieties of the organophosphate pesticides are available in the market of Ajmer. It was reported during the survey that Malathion (24%) was highest consumed organophosphate pesticide followed by dimethoate (19%) and monocrotophos (16%), respectively. To assess the effect of these pesticides on vegetables and to know about the residual level of these pesticides in cabbage and cauliflower fruits, a detailed study was conducted. The cabbage and cauliflower samples were collected from Palbichhla, Ramganj, Kotda and Khanpura area of Ajmer, where these crops are cultivated extensively.

The results of the present investigation reveals that the range of residues of different organophosphate pesticides was found as malathion > dimethoate > monocrotophos (Table 2 a-c). The highest average concentration of malathion was reported at Ramganj site in

Table 2 a. Contamination level of malathion, in ppm

Sampling site	Cauliflower			Cabbage		
	Min	Max	Ave	Min	Max	Ave
Palbichhla	1.36	3.96	1.92	0.73	1.82	1.05
Ramganj	1.85	4.26	2.65	1.26	3.29	1.82
Khanpura	0.74	1.94	0.98	bdl	1.37	0.68
Kotda	1.11	2.38	1.37	0.88	2.05	1.44

Table 2 b. Contamination level of dimethoate, in ppm

Sampling site	Cauliflower			Cabbage		
	Min	Max	Ave	Min	Max	Ave
Palbichhla	0.58	1.54	0.86	bdl	0.46	0.12
Ramganj	0.34	1.86	0.88	0.21	1.54	0.51
Khanpura	0.42	0.95	0.64	0.12	0.55	0.27
Kotda	0.03	0.58	0.16	0.47	0.71	0.53

Table 2 c. Contamination level of monocrotophos, in ppm

Sampling site	Cauliflower			Cabbage		
	Min	Max	Ave	Min	Max	Ave
Palbichhla	0.28	0.98	0.74	bdl	0.08	0.05
Ramganj	0.39	1.05	0.62	bdl	0.15	0.05
Khanpura	0.05	0.88	0.39	bdl	0.49	0.18
Kotda	0.05	0.29	0.11	bdl	0.09	0.05

both cauliflower (2.65 ppm) and cabbage (1.82 ppm), while its lowest average level was reported as 0.68 ppm in cabbage and 0.98 ppm in cauliflower at Khanpura sampling site. The results of the study are in fair linearity with the earlier findings (Tiwari, 1995; Charan, 2011), who assessed the effects of organophosphorus pesticides on ecophysiological aspects of some selected vegetable crops of Ajmer. Similarly, the highest average level of residues of dimethoate was reported as 0.88 ppm in cauliflower at Ramganj and 0.53 ppm in cabbage collected from Kotda, while it was noticed that lowest average level of dimethoate was 0.12 ppm in cabbage collected from Palbichhla and 0.16 ppm in cauliflower collected from Kotda. The results of the present investigation are in agreement with the outcome of the study carried out for

residue determination of dimethoate in leafy vegetables in Coimbatore (Bagyalakshmi *et al.*, 2011).

The highest average concentration of Monocrotophos was reported as 0.74 ppm in cauliflower and 0.18 ppm in cabbage collected from Palbichhla and Khanpura, respectively. Similarly, the lowest average concentration of monocrotophos was analyzed in cauliflower samples collected from Kotda, while it was lowest (0.05 ppm) in the cabbage collected from all sites, except Khanpura. A similar result to that identified for insecticide use in cabbage pest management in the Cameron Highlands Malaysia by Mazlan and Mumford (2005) was observed. It is observed that in most of the samples of cauliflower and cabbage were found under the maximum permissible limit

Table 3. Comparative effect of selected organophosphate pesticides on cauliflower

Treatment		Shoot length, cm	Root length, cm	Chl. a	Chl. b	Carote-noid	Protein	Lipid	Starch
Malathion	High	50.0 ± 0.38	13.0 ± 0.10	1.032 ± 0.112	0.0098 ± 0.007	0.248 ± 0.032	202 ± 13.29	-	0.492 ± 0.044
	Low	54.7 ± 0.65	24.5 ± 0.04	1.048 ± 0.084	0.0200 ± 0.004	0.229 ± 0.013	225 ± 12.11	0.040 ± 0.005	0.450 ± 0.038
Dimethoate	High	58.0 ± 0.44	16.1 ± 0.23	1.059 ± 0.329	0.0183 ± 0.006	0.265 ± 0.022	180 ± 13.70	-	0.435 ± 0.034
	Low	60.9 ± 0.71	24.4 ± 0.09	1.092 ± 0.276	0.0215 ± 0.003	0.293 ± 0.078	200 ± 14.58	0.011 ± 0.002	0.440 ± 0.029
Monocrotophos	High	65.0 ± 0.57	20.8 ± 0.52	1.088 ± 0.103	0.0195 ± 0.002	0.270 ± 0.050	179 ± 13.18	-	0.449 ± 0.065
	Low	72.5 ± 0.49	24.7 ± 0.13	1.065 ± 0.141	0.0210 ± 0.010	0.277 ± 0.044	215 ± 15.43	0.010 ± 0.001	0.460 ± 0.056
Control	-	59.2 ± 0.89	19.0 ± 0.32	1.079 ± 0.182	0.0228 ± 0.004	0.285 ± 0.016	175 ± 12.53	0.030 ± 0.004	0.420 ± 0.017

Table 4. Comparative effect of selected organophosphate pesticides on cabbage

Treatment		Shoot length, cm	Root length, cm	Chl. a	Chl. b	Carote-noid	Protein	Lipid	Starch
Malathion	High	42.0 ± 0.12	14.0 ± 0.15	1.512 ± 0.13	0.0178 ± 0.01	0.252 ± 0.04	198 ± 10.22	-	0.515 ± 0.18
	Low	49.2 ± 0.15	21.5 ± 0.05	1.187 ± 0.09	0.0221 ± 0.04	0.319 ± 0.05	215 ± 0.91	0.035 ± 0.02	0.480 ± 0.08
Dimethoate	High	48.0 ± 0.25	16.6 ± 0.21	1.175 ± 0.32	0.021 ± 0.005	0.277 ± 0.015	176 ± 5.50	-	0.358 ± 0.04
	Low	50.2 ± 0.50	19.0 ± 0.05	1.000 ± 0.11	0.0285 ± 0.005	0.313 ± 0.08	185 ± 6.58	0.05 ± 0.005	0.390 ± 0.02
Monocrotophos	High	51.0 ± 0.70	20.5 ± 0.55	1.885 ± 0.15	0.0190 ± 0.005	0.280 ± 0.05	153 ± 10.0	-	0.491 ± 0.05
	Low	52.5 ± 0.09	23.7 ± 0.05	1.955 ± 0.44	0.0210 ± 0.025	0.285 ± 0.01	205 ± 10.25	0.015 ± 0.001	0.505 ± 0.05
Control	-	40.5 ± 0.90	15.0 ± 0.55	1.085 ± 0.15	0.0225 ± 0.005	0.158 ± 0.08	186 ± 9.50	0.026 ± 0.005	0.453 ± 0.06

(MRL) for malathion, dimethoate and monocrotophos.

Effect of pesticide on phyto-chemical parameter of selected vegetable

In general, study indicates that the average

concentrations of different phyto-chemical parameters including chlorophyll-a, chlorophyll-b, carotenoids, protein, lipids and starch in selected vegetables were decreased on increasing the level of concentration of various pesticides. The effect of low dose (2 ppm)

and high dose (5 ppm) of selected pesticide on both, cauliflower and cabbage, were compared with the controlled (0 ppm) crop (Tables 3 and 4). Results on quantitative estimation of different biochemicals suggest that pesticides generally inhibit the synthesis of different biochemicals, which are generally expressed as retarded substantial growth in plants. In such effects, concentration of the pesticide is determination of inhibitory effects. Jaiswal *et al.* (1973) reported that substituted hydrocarbon insecticides when applied as spray decreased the soluble carbohydrates. Chopade *et al.* (2007) identified the effect of indiscriminate use of common insecticides on the essential catabolic activity of some vegetables. Low concentration of pesticides was found to increase the total sugars in plants. It is expected that trend of sugar content is in corroboration with starch content in vegetables of similar nature. Pesticides affect the nutritional level adversely through absorption, translocation and metabolism (Berger and Cwick, 1990). Similarly, pesticides were found to be inhibitory in increasing the lipid content of vegetable plants. Data reveal that higher concentration pesticides decreases level of lipids in different seasonal vegetables.

Data collected in the present investigation reveals that low concentration of pesticides favour of plants alongwith physiological and biochemical processes involved in synthesis of organic compounds, such as chlorophylls, carotenoides, sugars, lipids, proteins. Such effects may be viewed in context of chemical profile of different vegetables given by ICMR (1980). It may be concluded that pesticides may cause drastic change in pigments, carbohydrates, proteins, fats, thus lead to changes in nutritive value of vegetable crops. However, ecological factors, like temperature, light, moistures, soils minerals status alongwith pH play an important role in deciding the nutritive value of many vegetable plant species.

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